

Digital vs Traditional: Factors Influencing Youth Preferences for Insurance

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Abstract :Insurance is undoubtedly an efficient tool for financial protection. But, the question remains: is traditional insurance still preferred by today's tech-savvy generation? The current study examines the effect of various insurance attributes on customer preferences for digital insurance. Data is collected from 255 young adults enrolled in postgraduate programs across Telangana and probit regression is employed for data analysis. The findings indicate a positive association between digital insurance preference and insurance attributes viz., ease of buying and affordability. A significant gender disparity is also observed, with men exhibiting a notably higher inclination towards digital insurance. This study offers insights for designing digital insurance products to effectively facilitate the transition of customers from traditional to digital platforms.

Keywords: Digital Insurance, Traditional Insurance, Insurance Penetration, Customer Preference.

Introduction

In today's VUCA environment, which stands for Volatility, Uncertainty, Complexity, and Ambiguity, society grapples with significant challenges. Insurance assumes a pivotal role in this landscape, acting as a vital risk management tool. It not only protects individuals and families, ensuring their financial security in times of adversity, but also helps mitigate the impact of unforeseen income losses Lin et al., (2019); Liu et al., (2023); Ul Din et al., (2017).

In this regard, Government of India has made remarkable progress in extending insurance access to the vast segments of population which remained excluded from insurance safety net Economic Survey, (2024). However, facilitating access doesn't necessarily translate into increased product usage Ravi & Singh, (2016). This may be because of lack of awareness, lack of tailored products, and low perceived need for insurance Kiwanuka & Sibindi, (2023); Mehta, (2018); Business Standard, (2023). As a result, a significant insurance gap exists in India, with both life and non-life coverage falling short.

The emergence of digital insurance has injected a renewed sense of optimism towards filling the insurance gap. Digital Insurance offers several benefits to customers such as ease of buying, efficiency in claim settlement, information availability and customer support, and

affordability. However, several critical issues such as lack of digital awareness, privacy concerns, and lack of personal touch Taylor et al., (2002) have hindered the expansion of digital insurance (Pahuja & Chitkara, (2016).

This study is an attempt to investigate how insurance attributes such as ease of buying, affordability, availability of information, customer support and assistance, efficiency in claim settlement, personalization, and trust levels impact customer preferences towards digital insurance. The data is collected from 255 young adults pursuing postgraduate studies across Telangana. A probit regression is employed to establish association between customer preferences towards digital insurance and insurance attributes such as ease of buying, affordability, and availability of information, customer support and assistance, efficiency in claim settlement, personalization, and trust levels.

The study finds a positive association between the preference for digital insurance and two insurance attributes viz., ease of buying and affordability. Furthermore, our analysis reveals a notable gender difference, with men demonstrating a significantly higher inclination towards digital insurance.

The present study makes a valuable contribution to the current body of literature by meticulously analysing the relative significance of each attribute in shaping customer preferences. This analysis is instrumental for policymakers as it provides actionable insights for designing digital insurance products that effectively facilitate the transition of customers from traditional to digital platforms. Such strategic design considerations are essential for ensuring a seamless and successful adoption of digital insurance among consumers.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides a review of the relevant literature, followed by the research design in Section 3. Section 4 presents the results, while Section 5 offers a discussion of the findings. Section 6 concludes the paper, and Section 7 highlights the limitations and suggests directions for future research.

Literature review

The global penetration of insurance is 7.2%, however, in India it is still at a mere 4.2%. There is a growing need to understand the consumer behavior in the Indian context to contemplate on their planning, procuring and utilization of insurance as a product NASSCOM, (2023). The emergence of digital technologies is changing consumer expectations and also, the way insurance is purchased and delivered as a product Zeier Röschmann et al., (2022).

Khare et al., (2012) stated that the usage of Internet as a delivery mechanism for financial services has been growing as it minimizes the need for customers to directly interact with the staff and is perceived to be more convenient for customers. However, it is very important to understand the attitudes of consumers as it is a very crucial factor in planning these self-servicing technologies. Jitendra Singh Chauhan, (2023) proposed that since consumers are more used to the conventional sources like insurance agents for insurance, it becomes important to understand what factors of online insurance instill the required confidence in them.

(TIBCO) defined digital insurers as reference to insurance companies that have a technology-first operation model to handle the sales and management of insurance policies. It has dramatically changed the way insurance service providers operate with the use of Artificial Intelligence (AI), Internet of Things (IoT), Robotics, etc. However, research from Jitendra Singh Chauhan, (2023); Pahuja & Chitkara, (2016) has identified several critical issues such as lack of digital awareness, privacy concerns, and lack of personal touch have hindered the expansion of digital insurance.

Research Design

The sample for the study consists of young adults studying post-graduation in different colleges across Telangana state. Young adults were chosen for four reasons. First, college students, as early adopters and heavy users of electronic devices like smartphones, PCs, and tablets Boulianne & Theocharis, (2020) are particularly well-positioned to engage with digital platforms. Second, use of internet is especially prominent among the youth Luthfia et al., (2021), making them a key demographic for digital financial products. Third, attitudes toward financial decisions are often formed at a young age and have significant cumulative effects over a lifetime De Beckker et al., (2021); Lührmann et al., (2015). Fourth, Indian law permits the purchase of financial products from the age of 18, allowing young adults to actively participate in financial markets.

Permission was formally requested from the college principals to distribute survey among their post-graduate students. Following approval, the survey was disseminated among students using google form and the participation was voluntary.

This research aims to study how different attributes associated with the insurance impact the preference for digital insurance. The dependent variable of the study is binary, with a value of 1 indicating a preference for digital insurance and a value of 0 indicating a preference for traditional insurance. The responses on insurance attributes were recorded using a seven-point Likert scale. A score of 1 signifies a strong preference for traditional insurance in that attribute, whereas a score of 7 indicates a strong preference for digital insurance.

A total of 255 responses were collected from 12 colleges. Given the binary nature of the dependent variable, a probit regression model was employed. The probit model is particularly suited for this analysis because it accounts for the latent, continuous propensity underlying the binary choice. It assumes that there is a continuous, unobserved variable that reflects the likelihood of preferring digital over traditional insurance. This latent variable is influenced by the various insurance attributes, such as ease of buying, affordability, and availability of information, customer support and assistance, efficiency in claim settlement, personalization, and trust levels.

4. Results

Table 1 presents the demographic characteristics of the respondents. 56.5% of our sample comprised female respondents, while male respondents constituted 43.5% of the total respondents. The data indicates that a significant majority of respondents, accounting for

84.4%, fell within the age group of 19-24 years. Following this group, respondents aged 25-30 years constituted 13.6% of the sample. In contrast, only 2% of the respondents were in the 31-37 years age group. As far as marital status is concerned, 91.8% of the respondents were unmarried and 8.2% of the respondents were married. The survey results indicate that 49.8% of the sample reported an annual family of up to Rs 100,000. Additionally, 24.3% of respondents reported an annual family income in the range of Rs 100,001-300,000, while 13.7% had an income between Rs 300,001-500,000. Furthermore, 12.2% of the sample reported an annual family income exceeding Rs 500,000. The distribution of respondents based on their residential background indicates that 58.4% of the sample resides in urban areas, 23.1% comes from rural areas, and 18.4% belongs to semi-urban locations. Regarding comfotability with digital technologies, the survey results indicate that 19.6% of respondents reported an intermediate level of proficiency, followed by 17.6% who reported moderate level skills. Additionally, 17.3% of sample reported being a beginner level, while 18.4% felt proficient enough with digital technologies. Moreover, 17.3% reported an advanced level of proficiency, 9.4% considered themselves experts, and only 0.4% indicated being at a novice level.

Table 1: Demographics

	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	111	43.5
Female	144	56.5
Age Distribution		
19-24 Years	215	84.4
25-30 Years	35	13.6
31-37 Years	5	2
Marital Status		
Un-Married	234	91.8
Married	21	8.2
Annual Family Income		
up to Rs 100,000	127	49.8
Rs 100,001-300,000	62	24.3
Rs 300,001-500,000	35	13.7
Above Rs 500,000	31	12.2
Locality		
Urban	149	58.4
Semi-Urban	47	18.4
Rural	59	23.1

Probit regression results are presented in table 2. We find a positive association between the preference for digital insurance and insurance attributes viz., ease of buying and affordability.

These findings indicate that a smoother purchasing process and more competitive pricing for digital insurance are significant influencers of digital insurance preference. Furthermore, our analysis reveals a notable gender difference, with men demonstrating a significantly higher inclination towards digital insurance.

Table 2: Probit Regression

VARIABLES	(1) Preference for Digital Insurance
Ease of Buying	0.331*** (0.082)
Affordability	0.185** (0.083)
Information Availability	0.077 (0.089)
Efficiency in Claim Settlement	0.040 (0.090)
Personal Touch	0.130 (0.093)
Level of Trust	0.070 (0.079)
Gender	0.583** (0.235)
Age	-0.049 (0.054)
Unmarried	-0.373 (0.529)
Annual Family Income	0.053 (0.117)
Father’s Educational Qualification	0.105 (0.120)
Mother’s Educational Qualification	-0.056 (0.133)
Rural	-0.068 (0.125)
Digital Expertise	-0.087 (0.066)
Constant	2.050 (1.564)
Observations	255
Robust	Yes

Standard errors in parentheses*** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1

Discussion

The findings of the study highlight the significant impact of two key attributes, namely ease of buying and affordability for the preference towards digital insurance. The advent of digital technology has substantially streamlined the insurance buying process, contributing significantly to the preference for digital insurance. Furthermore, the cost efficiencies associated with digital platforms have led to more competitive pricing, enhancing the attractiveness of digital insurance for cost-conscious consumers.

In examining gender disparities, the study reveals that preferences for digital insurance are shaped by more than just demographic factors; they are influenced by underlying behavioural tendencies. These findings highlight the complex interplay between individual behaviour and technological advancements in shaping insurance choices.

While the variable of personal touch had a small, though not statistically significant, impact on digital insurance preference, it is still worth noting. This finding suggests that despite the emphasis on digital convenience, some consumers still value a personal connection. Insurers might consider enhancing their customer communication strategies to offer a more personalized experience, which could help bridge the gap between digital efficiency and the desire for personal interaction.

Overall, these results suggest that the rise of digital insurance is not merely a trend driven by convenience and cost but is also influenced by deeper behavioural dynamics.

Conclusion

Digital insurance is preferred more than traditional models of insurance among the youth in particular. Insurers who are still thinking about adopting digital insurance can consider doing it as soon as possible owing to its benefits. The transition from traditional to digital will actually help insurer leverage the resilient structure of the traditional system and use the analytics of the traditional models to better equip themselves with the usage of digital technologies.

Insurance is directly linked to more than five SDG's. Improved insurance penetration can lead to better outcomes on all these goals. Considering the preferences of the consumers, insurers can design inclusive insurance products that will improve the accessibility and affordability of insurance. Adopting digital insurance can help in achieving this goal as faster and efficient as possible.

This study makes a valuable contribution to the current body of literature by meticulously analysing the relative significance of each attribute in shaping customer preferences. This analysis is instrumental for policymakers and insurers alike as it provides actionable insights for designing digital insurance products that effectively facilitate the transition of customers from traditional to digital platforms. Such strategic design considerations are essential for ensuring a seamless and successful adoption of digital insurance among consumers.

Limitations and future scope

The study offers valuable insights into the factors influencing youth preferences for digital versus traditional insurance, but it has some limitations. First, the cross-sectional design limits the ability to establish causality, as it captures data at a single point in time. Additionally, the focus on postgraduate students may not fully represent the broader population. Future research could address these gaps by including more diverse demographic groups and conducting longitudinal studies to better understand how various insurance attributes influence customer preferences over time.

References

- Boulianne, S., & Theocharis, Y. 2020, Young people, digital media, and engagement: A meta-analysis of research. *Social science computer review*, 38(2), 111-127.
- De Beckker, K., De Witte, K., & Van Campenhout, G. 2021, The effect of financial education on students' consumer choices: Evidence from a randomized experiment. *Journal of Economic Behavior & Organization*, 188, 962-976.
- finance, M. o. 2024. *Economic Survey 2023-2024*. D. o. e. Affairs.
- Jitendra Singh Chauhan, P. S. 2023, Concept and Reasons of Growth for Online Insurance Penetration in India. *European Economic Letters*, 13(1)(2023), <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.52783/eel.v13i1.180>
- Khare, A., Dixit, S., Chaudhary, R., Kochhar, P., & Mishra, S. 2012, Customer behavior toward online insurance services in India. *Journal of Database Marketing & Customer Strategy Management*, 19, 120-133.
- Kiwanuka, A., & Sibindi, A. B. 2023, Insurance Literacy: Significance of Its Dimensions for Insurance Inclusion in Uganda. *Economies*, 11(2), 33.
- Lin, X., Bruhn, A., & William, J. 2019, Extending financial literacy to insurance literacy: A survey approach. *Accounting & Finance*, 59, 685-713.
- Liu, B., Yin, W., Chen, G., & Yao, J. 2023, The threshold effect of climate risk and the non-linear role of climate policy uncertainty on insurance demand: Evidence from OECD countries. *Finance Research Letters*, 55, 103820.
- Lührmann, M., Serra-Garcia, M., & Winter, J. 2015, Teaching teenagers in finance: Does it work? *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 54, 160-174.
- Luthfia, A., Wibowo, D., Widyakusumastuti, M. A., & Angeline, M. 2021, The role of digital literacy on online opportunity and online risk in Indonesian youth. *Asian Journal for Public Opinion Research*, 9(2), 142-160.
- Mehta, K. 2018, 18th April 2018, Four reasons why Indians buy such little general insurance. *Mint*.
- NASSCOM, I. L. G. L. 2023, *Digitalizing Insurance - Indian end-consumer perspective*.

Pahuja, A., & Chitkara, S. 2016, Perceptual exploration of factors and issues affecting adoption of e-insurance. Available at SSRN 2810005.

Ravi, S., & Singh, R. 2016, Nutrition in India: Targeting the First 1,000 Days of a Child's Life. Available at SSRN 3041157.

Standard, B. 2023, Over 40 crore in India don't have health insurance. *Business Standard*.

Taylor, S. A., Celuch, K., & Goodwin, S. 2002, Technology readiness in the e-insurance industry: an exploratory investigation and development of an agent technology e-consumption model. *Journal of Insurance Issues*, 142-165.

TIBCO. *What is digital insurance?* TIBCO. Retrieved 4-09-2024 from <https://www.tibco.com/glossary/what-is-digital-insurance>

Ul Din, S. M., Abu-Bakar, A., & Regupathi, A. 2017, Does insurance promote economic growth: A comparative study of developed and emerging/developing economies. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 5(1), 1390029.

Zeier Röschmann, A., Erny, M., & Wagner, J. 2022, On the (future) role of on-demand insurance: market landscape, business model and customer perception. *The Geneva Papers on Risk and Insurance-Issues and Practice*, 47(3), 603-642.